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Changes in Biological and Chemical Soil Properties in an Austrian Long-Term Tillage Experiment

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ABSTRACT

Conventional tillage, including ploughing after harvest and/or for seedbed preparation, aims to incorporate crop residues and weeds and to loosen, mix and aerate the soil. However, less beneficial effects, such as a loss of soil organic carbon (SOC), are also associated with intensive tillage. This has made reduced and minimum tillage systems without ploughing increasingly popular in agriculture, contributing to soil health and climate change mitigation. We studied the effects of different tillage systems on chemical and microbial soil properties in a long-term field experiment established on a fine-sandy loamy Haplic Chernozem in Fuchsenbigl, Austria, in 1988. The tillage treatments include conventional tillage (CT) with a plough and a cultivator down to 30 cm soil depth, reduced tillage (RT) with a cultivator down to 15 cm two to three times a year, as well as minimum tillage (MT) treated with a rotary driller once a year down to 5–8 cm soil depth. In 2016, a soil sampling campaign was conducted, and alkaline phosphatase, phospholipid fatty acids (PLFAs), and the nitrogen (N) mineralisation potential were analysed along with chemical properties including SOC, active C, total nitrogen (N_t), CAL extractable phosphorus (P_{CAL}) and potassium (K_{CAL}). Under MT, these properties were significantly higher compared to CT in 0–10 cm. In deeper soil layers, these parameters showed very few significant differences between the tillage treatments. RT yielded intermediate values but not always significantly different from CT. PLFA indicators significantly correlated with SOC and, even more distinctly, with N_t and active carbon. The high ratio of Gram-positive to Gram-negative bacteria indicates more recalcitrant organic matter in the top layer in MT than CT.

1 | Introduction

Soil microorganisms perform key roles in biogeochemical cycling and support ecosystem services and soil functions such as productivity, carbon cycling and storage, nutrient dynamics, provision, and biodiversity (Creamer et al. 2022; Labouyrie et al. 2023; Roger-Estrade et al. 2010; Schröder et al. 2016; Schulte et al. 2014; Van de Broek et al. 2019). Agricultural soil management practices, for example, tillage, can affect soil microbial communities and

their activity over time and space (Crittenden and de Goede 2016; Degrunne et al. 2017; Kandeler and Böhm 1996; Kandeler, Tscherko, and Spiegel 1999; Kandeler et al. 2001; Nivelles et al. 2016).

Tillage is applied for several reasons in agricultural soils, e.g., to evenly distribute nutrients, prevent plant diseases such as pathogenic fungi, remove weeds, aerate the soil, and prepare the seedbed to increase crop yields (Anderson et al. 2017; Roger-Estrade et al. 2010). Tillage systems are differentiated depending on the

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Summary

- Alkaline phosphatase and phospholipid fatty acids (PLFAs) were analysed in a long-term tillage field experiment.
- Alkaline phosphatase levels remained stable for more than two decades.
- PLFA markers for AMF showed the highest increase with minimum tillage compared to conventional tillage.
- Microbial indicators changed faster and are more sensitive to detecting tillage changes than chemical indicators.

frequency and extent of soil inversion. Under conventional tillage, the soil is ploughed (full inversion) and then harrowed, whereas in reduced and minimum non-inversion tillage systems, the soil is loosened with different intensity and depth without inversion. In no-tillage (no-till) systems, the soil is not disturbed in any way apart from seeding and harvest (Van Capelle, Schrader, and Brunotte 2012; Klik and Rosner 2020). Reduced tillage is increasingly replacing conventional tillage in American and European agriculture (Büchi et al. 2017; Kassam, Friedrich, and Derpsch 2018; Zuber and Villamil 2016). This is due to its lower costs and role in preventing soil degradation (e.g., erosion) (Achankeng and Cornelis 2023; Auzins et al. 2023). In an Austrian long-term tillage experiment, however, a compaction zone occurred below each tilled layer, even under reduced and minimum tillage (Weninger et al. 2020). Abandoning ploughing also makes weed control more challenging, boosting herbicide usage (Alletto et al. 2010).

Changes in tillage can impact soil chemical, physical, and biological indicators (Klik and Rosner 2020; Neugschwandtner et al. 2014, 2020, 2022; Sae-Tun et al. 2022; Toth et al. 2024; Xu et al. 2020). For instance, reduced tillage improves soil structure and aggregate stability and positively affects water content, aeration, and soil temperature (Kladivko 2001; Van Capelle, Schrader, and Brunotte 2012). In contrast to continuous conventional tillage, reduced tillage increases macroaggregates, soil organic carbon (SOC), and soil moisture but decreases porosity and oxygen diffusion (Zhang et al. 2018). Swędrzyńska and Małeczka-Jankowiak (2017) indicate that tillage influences soil carbon (C) cycling by its effects on soil microbial activities, which has been corroborated by several studies. A review of European long-term field experiments (Sandén et al. 2018) showed that non-inversion tillage significantly increases SOC concentrations as well as earthworm number and biomass compared to conventional tillage. D'Hose et al. (2018) report that under shallow non-inversion tillage, microbial biomass C increases significantly in the topsoil (< 10 cm), although no significant differences occurred at deeper depths (10–30 cm, > 30 cm). Increased microbial activity due to minimum tillage can affect important soil transformation processes, such as pesticide degradation. Jacobsen and Hjelmsø (2014) point out that an increase in the population of microorganisms can lead to faster degradation of pesticides. However, the rate of pesticide degradation by different tillage practices is still controversially debated in the literature (see review by Alletto et al. 2010).

Moreover, different tillage practices influence the composition and spatial distribution of soil microbial communities as well

as the ratio between fungi and bacteria and cause differences in soil microbial properties (Kandeler and Böhm 1996; Kandeler, Tscherko, and Spiegel 1999; Naz et al. 2023; Panettieri et al. 2020). Lupwayi et al. (2017) used phospholipid fatty acid (PLFA) biomarkers to determine soil microbial biomass and found significantly higher biomass in a conservation versus conventional agriculture system. They also reported a positive correlation between the amount of organic carbon added to the soil and the abundance of fungi and bacteria. Changes in chemical, physical, and microbial soil parameters affect soil organic matter decomposition and nutrient cycling (Anderson et al. 2017; Liang, Schimel, and Jastrow 2017; Wang et al. 2017). Microbial properties such as PLFAs, which are used to characterise the microbial community, soil enzyme activities (e.g., alkaline phosphatase), and potential nitrogen (N) mineralisation are acknowledged indicators for changes of ecosystem functioning in agricultural soils (Athmann et al. 2017; Spiegel et al. 2018; Zelles 1999; Zhang et al. 2018). According to Woloszczyk et al. (2020), more glucose-responsive microorganisms occur in tilled croplands compared to relatively undisturbed grassland. This points to higher amounts of easily degradable SOC and less stable SOC stocks in intensively managed soils. Furthermore, cover crops and no-till, as compared to conventional tillage, have been shown to increase the activity of phosphatase (Tyler 2020). This effect was attributed to the higher amounts of substrate and microbial biomass. In an earlier study based on our long-term tillage experiment in Fuchsenbigl, the potential N mineralisation showed a significant linear correlation with the active soil organic matter pool (Franko and Spiegel 2016). Moreover, enhanced alkaline phosphatase activity and potential N mineralisation may improve the supply of the plant nutrients phosphorus (P) and N under different tillage practices. Mann et al. (2019) suggested including PLFA analysis in regular analyses of agricultural soils, based on the correlations they detected between soil health assessments and PLFA profiles. PLFA has an advantage over DNA community assessments in that it depicts the abundance of functional groups in the soil, which may help explain differences in soil development under different management methods.

This study was designed to present the short- and long-term development of chemical and biological soil properties in an Austrian long-term tillage experiment. It is known that some soil parameters (e.g., SOC) hardly change over many years, while others, especially microbial parameters, react quickly to management changes such as tillage and therefore allow an early assessment of this type of management (Kandeler, Tscherko, and Spiegel 1999). SOC, N mineralisation potential, and alkaline phosphatase activity were analysed using the same methodology over many years, yielding long-term data beyond that provided in the former publications of Kandeler, Tscherko, and Spiegel (1999) and Spiegel et al. (2007).

After the start of the field experiment, selected microbial parameters, including enzymes, were analysed for several years until 1997 (see Kandeler, Tscherko, and Spiegel 1999) and beyond. This measurement campaign ended in 2002 and was to be continued in 2016. However, it turned out that alkaline phosphatase was the only enzyme for which the test method had not changed, and the results could therefore be compared with those of previous years.

In 2016, samples were taken, and a range of additional soil properties were measured once, along with PLFAs (including

arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF)), to highlight the effect of management on the main microbial groups. This work is a synthesis of existing data and a broader selection of analytical methods. The aim of this study was to examine the extent to which different tillage treatments change chemical and microbiological soil properties over a period of 28 years. We hypothesise that soil microbiological properties indicate changes due to different soil tillage after a relatively short period of time (a few years), while soil organic matter (SOC) needs at least a decade to detect the adaptations to the new soil management. Another hypothesis is that tillage changes the spatial distribution of crop residues in the top 30 cm of soil in the long term and that this has consequences for microbial colonisation. We therefore assume that reduced tillage will lead to an increased accumulation of crop residues in the top 10 cm of the soil and that soil microorganisms in this soil layer can therefore increase both their biomass and their activity.

2 | Materials and Methods

2.1 | Experimental Site

At the AGES research station Fuchsenbigl in Lower Austria (48°12' N, 16°44' E, 147 m altitude), a field experiment established in 1988 has been examining the effects of three tillage treatments on soil

and crops (Hendricks et al. 2022; Spiegel, Pfeffer, and Hösch 2002; Spiegel et al. 2007). The tillage treatments are:

- conventional tillage (CT): stubble cultivation with a cultivator after the harvest, basic soil cultivation with a mouldboard plough to a depth of 25–30 cm (inversion tillage), and seedbed preparation with a seedbed combination
- reduced tillage (RT) with a cultivator (non-inversion tillage) twice a year—after the harvest and before seedbed preparation with a seedbed combination—to a depth of ca. 15 cm, and
- minimum tillage (MT) using a rotary driller without any primary treatment once a year before seeding, with a cultivation depth of 5–8 cm.

All treatments were laid out in a randomised complete block design with three replications. The overall trial area is 6480 m². The plots are located side by side, each plot measuring 60 m × 12 m (= 720 m²). The crop rotation, the fertilization and the crop yields from 1998 to 2016 are shown in Table 1. The same crops were used across the different tillage treatments. No cover crops were included in the crop rotation. Crop residues remained on the field in all treatments. Fertilisation was done according to the Austrian guidelines for fertilisation (e.g., BMLFUW 2017). The soil is classified as a fine-sandy

TABLE 1 | Crops, fertilisation (N: Nitrogen, P: Phosphorus, K: Potassium), and yields of the tillage experiment Fuchsenbigl (MT: Minimum tillage, RT: Reduced tillage, CT: Conventional tillage) during 1998–2016.

Year	Crop	Fertilisation (kg ha ⁻¹)			Yields (t ha ⁻¹)		
		N	P	K	MT	RT	CT
1998	Spring wheat	100	26	50	3.166 a	2.777 a	3.021 a
1999	Spring barley	50	20	75	3.760 a	5.181 b	5.429 b
2000	Winter wheat	120	22	42	2.692 a	2.691 a	2.996 a
2001	Sugar beet	100	39	149	63.322 a	60.306 a	63.214 a
2002	Spring wheat	100	22	42	3.077 a	3.037 a	2.723 a
2003	Maize	120	28	125	6.953 a	6.329 a	7.027 a
2004	Winter wheat	120	0	0	5.235 a	4.977 a	5.125 a
2005	Spring wheat	100	22	42	2.439 b	2.104 a	2.500 b
2006	Maize	120	33	125	5.346 a	6.686 a	7.164 a
2007	Winter wheat	120	15	0	3.864 c	3.369 a	3.640 b
2008	Sugar beet	100	0	0	54.861 a	67.546 b	71.528 c
2009	Spring barley	80	24	66	2.639 a	3.287 a	2.963 a
2010	Maize	120	33	125	5.796 a	6.839 b	7.614 b
2011	Winter wheat	120	15	0	3.568 b	2.590 a	3.328 b
2012	Winter barley	110	20	25	2.315 a	2.940 b	2.955 b
2013	Soybean	0	0	0	3.287 a	3.556 a	3.616 a
2014	Winter wheat	120	20	33	3.743 a	3.190 a	3.576 a
2015	Maize	120	33	125	3.653 a	4.451 b	4.871 b
2016	Winter wheat	120	0	0	4.165 a	4.164 a	4.448 a

Note: Different letters indicate significant treatment differences according to Tukey's significance test ($p < 0.05$).

loamy Haplic Chernozem (FAO 2006) with 220 g kg⁻¹ clay, 410 g kg⁻¹ silt, and 370 g kg⁻¹ sand. On average, soils at this experimental site had a pH of 7.6, 130 g kg⁻¹ CaCO₃, 17.1 g kg⁻¹ soil organic carbon (SOC), and 1.6 g kg⁻¹ N_t in 0–30 cm (Kandeler, Tscherko, and Spiegel 1999; units adapted). The mean annual temperature is 9.4°C, and the mean long-term annual precipitation is 529 mm.

2.2 | Soil Sampling and Preparation

Soil samples were collected yearly in March or April (before fertiliser application) approximately at field capacity at depths of 0–10, 10–20 and 20–30 cm. On each plot, 16 sub-samples were taken with a single-gouge auger (cores of 30 mm diameter); these were mixed and stored in plastic bags. For chemical analyses and N mineralisation potential, the soil samples were air-dried and sieved <2 mm, for soil microbial analyses, the samples were stored in plastic bags at 4°C. Within 2 weeks the samples were sieved (<2 mm) and analysed, otherwise, they were deep frozen at –18°C.

2.3 | Chemical Soil Properties

Soil organic carbon (SOC) concentrations of the soil samples were determined annually by dry combustion in a LECO RC-612 TruMac CN (LECO Corp., St. Joseph, MI, USA) at 650°C (ÖNORM L1080) from 1998 to 2016. In 1989 the initial SOC was analysed by wet combustion with the method of Walkley and Black (1934). The organic matter was oxidised by K₂Cr₂O₇ and H₂SO₄ (without external heating) and measured by photometry (ÖNORM L 1081). These values were multiplied by the conversion factor 1.44 for comparison with the dry combustion data set as described in Spiegel et al. (2007). Active carbon (C) was analysed with potassium permanganate (KMnO₄) to determine the active C (AC) pool, a labile soil C fraction, with a titration of the 0.02 M KMnO₄ solution with sodium oxalate (Na₂C₂O₄) according to Tatzber et al. (2015). N_t was analysed according to ÖNORM EN 16168 by elemental analysis using a CNS 2000 SGA-410-06 at 1250°C. Plant-available phosphorus (P_{CAL}) and potassium (K_{CAL}) were determined by calcium-acetate-lactate (CAL) extraction (ÖNORM L1087) with a spectral photometer (P) and flame photometer (K) using a Segmented Flow Analyser SAN (Skalar). Plant-available P and K indicate the availability of these important plant nutrients, which can be utilised by the crops over a period of 4–6 years. Exchangeable cations—calcium (Ca), potassium (K), magnesium (Mg), sodium (Na or NABV)-and Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC) were determined according to ÖNORM L1086-1 using an unbuffered 0.1 M BaCl₂ solution and ICP-OES (Thermo Fisher ICP-ICAP 6500). Soil pH was measured electrochemically (pH/mV Pocket Meter pH 340i, WTW, Weilheim, Germany) in 0.01 M CaCl₂ at a soil: solution ratio of 1:2.5 (ÖNORM EN ISO 10390). The dry matter content (%) of the soil was determined according to ÖNORM EN 15934 at 105°C and provides an indication of the water content (100 minus dry matter content). This demonstrates which tillage treatments lead to a higher soil moisture, which is especially important for crop production in dry periods under climate change conditions.

2.4 | Microbial Soil Properties

2.4.1 | Alkaline Phosphomonoesterase (Phosphatase) Activity

Alkaline phosphatase activity was analysed annually between 1989 and 2002 and, again, in 2016 in three soil depths (0–10, 10–20, 20–30 cm). We combined the already published data from 1989 to 2002 (Kandeler, Tscherko, and Spiegel 1999) with the new data from 2016. Alkaline phosphatase (alkaline phosphomonoesterase) activity was assayed using a modified disodium phenylphosphate method: 5 g of soil were incubated in 10 mL of 20 mM borate buffer (pH 10.0) and 5 mL of 20 mM buffered disodium phenylphosphate solution at 37°C for 3 h; released phenol was estimated by a colour reaction (Hoffmann 1968).

2.4.2 | N Mineralisation Potential

The nitrogen (N) mineralisation potential of dried soils was measured from 2002 to 2016 by anaerobic incubation (Keeney 1982), modified according to Kandeler (1993). Soil samples (5.0 g) were incubated under waterlogged conditions in enclosed tubes with little headspace at 40°C for 7 days (Keeney 1982; ÖNORM L1204).

The N mineralisation potential (anaerobic incubation) is a commonly used biological soil parameter that indicates the N cycle in the soil–plant system. Waterlogged conditions are used to ensure mineralisation of organic N compounds to ammonium, but to avoid nitrification, which would make it necessary to measure nitrate as well. Therefore, ammonium is the only final product of the mineralisation process. There is a good correlation ($r=0.96$) between aerobic and anaerobic N mineralisation (Waring and Bremner 1964) in Schinner et al. (1993). The N mineralisation potential has been analysed with the same methods for (more than) 17 years and therefore provides comparable results over the years. It also provides information on the abundance of easily mineralisable substances and the activity of the microorganisms involved. This parameter can be tested in routine analysis, and the results can also be used by farmers to optimise N fertilisation.

2.4.3 | Phospholipid Fatty Acid and Neutral Lipid Fatty Acid Analysis (Microbial Community Structure)

Extraction of lipids and separation into neutral lipid fatty acids (NLFA) and phospholipid fatty acids (PLFAs) were done according to Frostegård, Tunlid, and Bååth (1991). Lipid fractionation and subsequent estimation of fatty acid methyl esters (FAMES) were performed according to Kramer et al. (2013). Data are expressed as nmol g⁻¹ soil dry weight (dw). The total PLFA was calculated based on all identified peaks assigned to microbes according to Frostegård and Bååth (1996). The PLFA was assigned to different functional groups according to Willers, Jansen van Rensburg, and Claassens (2015) (Table 3 and Table S1). The NLFA 16:1ω5 was used as a biomarker for storage products of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) (Ruess and Chamberlain 2010; Olsson and Johansen 2000). PLFAs were determined in 2016 only.

2.4.4 | Statistical Analysis

All analytical results were computed as arithmetic means of results from three plots in the soil depths of 0–10, 10–20 and 20–30 cm. Statistical analysis involved a multiple analysis of variance and subsequent multiple range tests (Tukey's honest significant difference). Correlations between variables were calculated with the Spearman correlation coefficient. The statistical analysis was performed using SPSS (version 20, IBM SPSS Statistics, USA) and R; the figures were created in R ggplot.

3 | Results

3.1 | Chemical Soil Properties

Thirteen years after the start of the experiment, in 2001, SOC concentrations—for the first time—increased significantly in 0–10 cm under MT compared to RT and CT (Figure 1). This was recorded in all investigated years thereafter. In 10–20 and 20–30 cm, no significant differences occurred between the tillage treatments, but since 2008, SOC often showed a tendency for the highest concentrations under long-term CT compared to MT and RT in 20–30 cm. Table 2 shows the chemical soil properties after 28 years of different tillage measures. In the 0–10 cm soil depth, in addition to SOC, active carbon, N_i and P_{CAL} were significantly higher under MT than CT. The C:N ratio was lowest under MT, significantly higher under reduced tillage, and intermediate under CT. The percentage increases were highest for plant-available K_{CAL} and P_{CAL} and less for active carbon, N_i and SOC after long-term MT compared to CT. A significant pH decrease occurred under MT compared to RT and CT, and dry matter contents increased in the order $MT < RT < CT$. No significant differences in the selected soil properties between the tillage variants occurred at 10–20 cm. In 20–30 cm, active carbon was significantly higher under long-term CT compared to RT, with intermediate values under MT. Dry matter contents were significantly lower under CT compared to RT and MT. Averaged over a depth of 0–30 cm, most soil properties did not show significant differences, except for the C:N ratio, which was significantly higher under CT than MT. The pH was lowest with MT compared to RT.

3.2 | Microbial Soil Properties

3.2.1 | Alkaline Phosphomonoesterase (Phosphatase) Activity and N Mineralisation Potential

From 1989 to 1995, the alkaline phosphatase activity significantly increased in MT and RT relative to CT within two experimental years (Figure 2). Thereafter it levelled out with MT higher than RT. In 2016, alkaline phosphatase values were similar to those of the previous data (1989–2002). Phosphatase activities were significantly higher after long-term MT compared to RT and CT in 0–10 cm in 2016. A tendency for higher activities in CT was recorded in 20–30 cm.

Figure 3 shows that the N mineralisation potential in 0–10 cm depth was highest under MT and lowest in CT, with RT in an intermediate position since 2000. In 2016, the N mineralisation

FIGURE 1 | Effect of minimum (MT) and reduced (RT) compared to conventional (CT) tillage on soil organic carbon concentrations in the (a) 0–10 cm, (b) 10–20 cm and (c) 20–30 cm soil layers in 1989 and from 1998 to 2016 (CT = 100%). Error bars: Standard errors.

potential under MT at 0–10 cm was $93.3 \text{ mg kg}^{-1} \text{ 7d}^{-1}$, more than twice as high as in CT ($42.6 \text{ mg kg}^{-1} \text{ 7d}^{-1}$; Table 3). According to the “Austrian guidelines for appropriate

TABLE 2 | Chemical soil properties under long-term minimum (MT), reduced (RT), and conventional (CT) tillage (mean values, $n = 3$) in 2016.

	Depth	CT	Significances	RT	Significances	MT	Significances	RT increase/ decrease compared to CT (=100)	MT increase/ decrease compared to CT (=100)
SOC g kg^{-1}	0–10cm	15.8	a A	17.0	a B	20.2	b B	108	128
	10–20cm	16.4	a A	15.9	a AB	15.4	a A	97	94
	20–30cm	16.2	a A	15.1	a A	15.4	a A	93	95
	0–30cm	16.1	a	16.0	a	17.0	a	99	106
active Carbon (KMnO_4) mg kg^{-1}	0–10cm	485	a A	510	a B	667	b B	105	138
	10–20cm	428	a A	461	a B	442	a A	108	103
	20–30cm	457	b A	364	a A	431	ab A	80	94
	0–30cm	457	a	445	a	514	a	97	112
N_t mg kg^{-1}	0–10cm	0.15	a A	0.16	a C	0.20	b B	107	133
	10–20cm	0.15	a A	0.15	a B	0.15	a A	100	100
	20–30cm	0.15	a A	0.14	a A	0.15	a A	93	100
	0–30cm	0.15	a	0.15	a	0.17	a	100	113
C:N	0–10cm	10.3	ab A	10.4	b A	10.0	a A	101	97
	10–20cm	10.8	a A	10.4	a A	10.1	a A	96	94
	20–30cm	10.8	a A	10.5	a A	10.3	a A	97	95
	0–30cm	10.7	b	10.4	ab	10.2	a	97	95
P_{CAL} mg kg^{-1}	0–10cm	95.3	a A	118	a C	160	b B	124	168
	10–20cm	97.7	a A	110	a B	88.3	a A	113	90
	20–30cm	92.7	a A	73.0	a A	87.0	a A	79	94
	0–30cm	95.2	a	100	a	112	a	105	118
K_{CAL} mg kg^{-1}	0–10cm	140	a A	237	ab C	279	b B	169	199
	10–20cm	143	a A	178	a B	173	a A	124	121
	20–30cm	139	a A	115	a A	159	a A	83	114
	0–30cm	141	a	177	a	204	a	126	145
CEC cmol_c kg^{-1}	0–10cm	21.4	a A	21.1	a A	22.5	a A	99	105
	10–20cm	21.7	a A	21.5	a A	21.9	a A	99	101
	20–30cm	22.2	a A	22.0	a A	21.1	a A	99	95
	0–30cm	21.8	a	21.5	a	21.8	a	99	100
$\text{pH}_{\text{CaCl}_2}$	0–10cm	7.60	b A	7.58	b A	7.48	a A	100	98
	10–20cm	7.57	a A	7.59	a AB	7.58	a A	100	100
	20–30cm	7.59	a A	7.62	a B	7.58	a A	100	100
	0–30cm	7.59	ab	7.60	b	7.55	a	100	99
Dry matter content %	0–10cm	84.8	c B	84.3	b A	82.5	a A	99	97
	10–20cm	84.1	a A	85.1	a A	84.5	a B	101	100
	20–30cm	83.7	a A	84.9	b A	85.0	b B	101	102
	0–30cm	84.2	a	84.8	a	84.0	a	101	100

Note: Different lowercase letters within one depth (row) indicate significant treatment differences, and different uppercase letters within one column indicate significant depth differences according to Tukey's significance test ($p < 0.05$).

TABLE 3 | Total phospholipid fatty acids (PLFA, nmol g⁻¹ dm) and neutral lipid fatty acids (NLFA, nmol g⁻¹ dm, assigned to arbuscular mycorrhiza fungi (AMF)), Total PLFA: SOC-ratio, Gram-positive: Gram-negative ratio, and the nitrogen (N) mineralisation potential under long-term minimum (MT), reduced (RT) and conventional (CT) tillage (mean values, n = 3) in 2016.

	Depth	CT	Signi- ficances	RT	Signi- ficances	MT	Signi- ficances	RT increase/decrease compared to CT (=100)	MT increase/ decrease compared to CT (=100)
Total PLFA	0–10 cm	29.9	a A	52.2	b B	73.6	c C	175	246
	10–20 cm	26.1	a A	26.7	a AB	27.1	a B	102	104
	20–30 cm	25.8	a A	20.5	a A	13.9	a A	79	54
NLFA 16:1 ω 5 AMF	0–30 cm	27.3	a	33.1	a	38.2	a	121	140
	0–10 cm	2.31	a A	3.02	a A	6.94	b B	131	300
	10–20 cm	2.59	a A	3.64	a A	4.16	a AB	141	161
Total PLFA: SOC-ratio	20–30 cm	2.37	a A	3.63	a A	3.17	a A	153	134
	0–30 cm	2.42	a	3.43	ab	4.76	b	142	197
	0–10 cm	18.79	a A	30.66	b A	36.44	c A	163	194
Gram-positive: Gram- negative ratio	10–20 cm	15.95	a A	16.61	a B	17.65	a B	104	111
	20–30 cm	15.89	a A	13.75	a B	8.99	a B	87	57
	0–30 cm	16.87	a	20.33	a	21.03	a	121	125
N mineralisation potential mg kg ⁻¹ 7d ⁻¹	0–10 cm	0.98	a A	0.92	a A	1.16	b A	94	118
	10–20 cm	1.09	a A	1.29	a B	1.32	a B	118	121
	20–30 cm	1.02	a A	1.30	b B	1.28	b B	127	125
N mineralisation potential mg kg ⁻¹ 7d ⁻¹	0–30 cm	1.03	a	1.17	ab	1.25	b	114	121
	0–10 cm	42.6	a A	69.7	b C	93.3	c B	164	219
	10–20 cm	45.1	a A	49.3	a B	42.2	a A	109	94
N mineralisation potential mg kg ⁻¹ 7d ⁻¹	20–30 cm	39.3	a A	31.0	a A	41.1	a A	79	105
	0–30 cm	42.3	a	50.0	a	58.9	a	118	139

Note: Different lowercase letters within one depth (row) indicate significant treatment differences, and different uppercase letters within one column indicate significant depth differences according to Tukey's significance test ($p < 0.05$).

a

b

c

FIGURE 2 | Effect of minimum (MT) and reduced (RT) compared to conventional (CT) tillage on alkaline phosphatase activity in the (a) 0–10 cm, (b) 10–20 cm and (c) 20–30 cm soil layers from 1989 to 2002 and in 2016 (CT = 100%). Error bars: Standard errors.

fertilisation” (BMLFUW 2017), the values were classified as high ($> 75 \text{ mg N kg}^{-1} 7\text{d}^{-1}$) under MT (with exceptions in 2004 and 2008) and low to medium ($35 \text{ to } 75 \text{ mg N kg}^{-1} 7\text{d}^{-1}$)

a

b

c

FIGURE 3 | Effect of minimum (MT) and reduced (RT) compared to conventional (CT) tillage on N mineralisation potential in the (a) 0–10 cm, (b) 10–20 cm and (c) 20–30 cm soil layers from 2000 to 2016 (CT = 100%). Error bars: Standard errors.

under RT and CT. No significant treatment differences were observed in the deeper soil layers or averaged over the depth of 0–30 cm.

FIGURE 4 | Effect of minimum (MT), reduced (RT) and conventional (CT) tillage on the total PLFA:SOC ratio in 0–10, 10–20 and 20–30 cm soil depths in 2016. Different lowercase letters within one depth indicate significant treatment differences, and different uppercase letters within one treatment indicate significant depth differences according to Tukey's significance test ($p < 0.05$).

3.2.2 | PLFAs

Table 3 shows the total amount of PLFAs as an indicator for microbial biomass (Frostegård, Tunlid, and Bååth 1991), and Table S1 indicates selected PLFAs as biomarkers for different functional groups of a microbial community according to Willers, Jansen van Rensburg, and Claassens (2015). The total PLFA and all PLFA biomarkers were highest under MT and lowest under CT in the surface soil layer 0–10 cm, partly with significant differences between the tillage variants. Under MT, total PLFAs increased by 146%, and under RT by 75% in 0–10 cm depth, with certain single PLFAs revealing even higher increases (Tables 3 and S1). Both the total PLFA and the total PLFA:SOC ratio in the top layer are much higher in the MT and RT treatments than under CT (Figure 4, Table 3). The total PLFA:SOC ratio decreased with depth for RT and MT but not CT. Many PLFAs, especially those assigned as bacterial markers, decreased with soil depth in all treatments, with MT exhibiting the strongest gradient and CT the weakest according to the soil depths. At 10–20 cm, only one PLFA assigned to Gram-positive bacteria ($\alpha 15:0$) was still significantly higher in MT compared to CT. At 20–30 cm, PLFAs were often higher under long-term CT compared to MT, but only $\text{cy}17:0$ assigned to Gram-negative bacteria and $18:2\omega 6$ assigned to saprotrophic fungi exceeded the significance threshold (Table S1). NLFA and PLFA 16:1 $\omega 5$, assigned to arbuscular mycorrhiza, showed the highest increases under MT compared to CT at 0–10 cm (Tables 3 and S1). For NLFA, the values averaged over the whole depth of 0–30 cm were significantly higher under long-term MT compared to CT. The ratio of Gram-positive (relatively more abundant in complex soil carbon environments (Fanin et al. 2019)) to Gram-negative (relatively more abundant in less complex soil carbon environments) bacteria was higher in MT than in CT and RT, especially in 0–10 cm (Table 3). Over 0–30 cm, MT had a significantly higher ratio than CT.

Table 4 presents Spearman correlation coefficients between the total PLFA, the PLFA and NLFA biomarkers for arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF), and soil properties ($n = 27$) in three soil

TABLE 4 | Spearman correlation coefficients between the total phospholipid fatty acids (PLFA), the PLFA biomarker for arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF), and the neutral lipid fatty acids (NLFA) biomarker for AMF, and selected soil properties ($n = 27$) in soil depths of 0–10, 10–20 and 20–30 cm in 2016.

	Total PLFA	PLFA 16:1 $\omega 5$ AMF	NLFA 16:1 $\omega 5$ AMF
SOC mg kg^{-1}	0.42*	0.44*	0.37
active Carbon (KMnO_4) mg kg^{-1}	0.49**	0.55**	0.33
N_t mg kg^{-1}	0.52**	0.56**	0.39*
C:N	−0.33	−0.37	−0.28
N mineralisation potential mg kg^{-1} 7d^{-1}	0.38*	0.42*	0.11
alkaline phosphatase μg Phenol $\text{g}^{-1} 3\text{h}^{-1}$	0.70**	0.70**	0.36
P_{CAL} mg kg^{-1}	0.38	0.45*	0.30
K_{CAL} mg kg^{-1}	0.31	0.37	0.29
CEC $\text{cmol}_c \text{kg}^{-1}$	0.21	0.21	0.41*
$\text{pH}_{\text{CaCl}_2}$	−0.25	−0.32	−0.47*
Dry matter content %	−0.40*	−0.41*	−0.60**

Note: Asterisks indicate significance at $p < 0.05$ (*) and $p < 0.01$ (**).

depths down to 30 cm in 2016. The total PLFA and the PLFA biomarker for AMF were highly ($p < 0.01$) positively correlated with N_t , active C, and alkaline phosphatase. A significant ($p < 0.05$) positive correlation of the total PLFA and the PLFA biomarker for AMF was determined with SOC and the N mineralisation potential, and a significant negative correlation with dry matter content. The NLFA biomarker for AMF showed highly significant ($p < 0.01$) negative correlations with dry matter content, a significant ($p < 0.05$) negative one with pH, and significant positive correlations with CEC and N_t .

4 | Discussion

Soil biological and soil chemical properties show that, within different time frames, tillage affects both the spatial distribution and the absolute level of these properties (Kandeler, Tscherko, and Spiegel 1999). However, it is still largely unclear when these properties settle to a new level.

4.1 | Chemical Soil Properties

Soil properties, especially nutrients and soil organic carbon, showed distinct depth gradients depending on the cultivation depth of the tillage treatments. This gradient was most distinct

in MT between the first (0–10 cm) and the second (10–20 cm) soil layer due to a cultivation depth less than 10 cm. A more even decrease of chemical soil properties with depth occurred under RT, where the soil is loosened to a depth of around 15 cm. Under CT, the soil components were most evenly distributed to a depth of 25/30 cm, resulting in comparatively higher values of some soil properties in the 20–30 cm depth under long-term CT (e.g., SOC, active carbon, P_{CAL}). Significant differences in chemical soil properties between treatments mainly occurred at 0–10 cm. The increase of SOC, N_t , and plant-available K in the topsoil under MT and RT, i.e., non-inversion tillage, was already indicated in Spiegel et al. (2007) and has also been reported by several other authors (D'Hose et al. 2016; Swędrzyńska and Małacka-Jankowiak 2017; Neugschwandtner et al. 2014; Sandén et al. 2018). An increase of SOC and N_t concentrations in the uppermost soil layer after reducing tillage was described by Mathew et al. (2012), Sipilä et al. (2012), Shi et al. (2012) Bai et al. (2019) as well. This reflects the accumulation of organic (e.g., crop, weed) residues in the top layer because they are not mixed with the deeper soil layers. The higher SOC concentrations may explain the higher water content recorded after reduced tillage (Dobrzeńcki et al. 2012). The temporal development of SOC in 0–10 cm indicates that this parameter reached statistically significant higher concentrations under MT compared to CT 13 years after the start of the experiment. This shows that increases in SOC due to minimal tillage require a considerable period of time and cannot be used as a short-term measure. Similar outcomes are reported by Mary et al. (2020), who found that SOC stabilised in less than 20 years after the start of the treatment. On the other hand, we did not find a continued decrease in soil carbon (SOC) in deeper soil layers. Bai et al. (2019), for example, reported such a decrease in 20–30 cm soil depth after shifting from CT to MT. The pH was significantly lower under MT in our study, which could reflect an enrichment of organic acids and microbial respiration with more soil organic matter in the topmost soil layer (Hulugalle and Weaver 2005). The low C:N ratio under long-term MT indicates soils with higher microbial activity because microbial biomass is rich in nitrogen (Ottow 2011). Surprisingly, the SOC in RT did not differ from the CT in 0–10 cm even though RT soil was mixed down to only 15 cm as compared to 25–30 cm in CT. One explanation could be that the tillage frequency and thus the mineralisation conditions were similar in both treatments. When averaging data from soil properties over a depth of 0–30 cm, only a few significant differences occurred. The C/N ratio was significantly higher under CT than MT and the pH was lowest under MT compared to RT. However, a limitation of using average data from the 0–10, 10–20, and 20–30 cm layers to calculate the values for the 0–30 cm depth could be that this approach might not be robust due to variations in bulk density across soil depths of the different tillage treatments.

4.2 | Microbial Soil Properties

4.2.1 | Alkaline Phosphomonoesterase (Phosphatase) Activity and N Mineralisation Potential

After long-term MT, alkaline phosphatase activities—an indicator for the decomposition of organic phosphorus compounds—were significantly higher compared to RT and CT in 0–10 cm. Comparable results were reported by Swędrzyńska and Małacka-Jankowiak (2017), who detected increased activities

in reduced tillage systems near the soil surface (0–10 cm) and lower ones in 10–20 cm compared to CT. Heidari, Mohammadi, and Sohrabi (2016) measured significantly higher activities under minimum tillage compared to conventional tillage even in 0–30 cm. In our experiment, Kandeler, Tscherko, and Spiegel (1999) highlighted alkaline phosphatase to display a distinct discrimination between the tillage variants already in the second year of different tillage practices. That discrimination increased quickly over the subsequent 6 years. Up to 2016, a reduction of tillage depth (RT and MT) and/or the frequency of tillage treatments (MT) influenced the habitat of soil microorganisms, especially in the uppermost 0–10 cm. At the same time, the higher activity of phosphatase, an enzyme that mineralises organically bound P to plant-available P (Schinner et al. 1993), may have promoted the higher amounts of P_{CAL} .

The strong depth gradient of microbiological properties such as microbial biomass (PLFA), N mineralisation potential, and enzyme activities under MT and RT compared to CT was already observed in the first years of this experiment (Kandeler and Böhm 1996; Kandeler, Tscherko, and Spiegel 1999). Other authors reported similar developments (e.g., Anderson et al. 2017; Büchi et al. 2017; Sun et al. 2018). This is because organic matter, mainly from plant residues, remained near the soil surface in MT or was incorporated down to a depth of around 15 cm in RT and down to 25/30 cm in CT, where it served as substrate for soil organisms. The results are also in line with Neugschwandtner et al. (2014), who detected higher potentially mineralisable N in 0–10 cm under shallow and deep conservation tillage compared to mouldboard ploughing. Moreover, our study revealed that this biological parameter mainly followed SOC. However, the differences between the variants were more distinct. Even more than alkaline phosphatase, the increase of the N mineralisation potential under MT was +119% compared to CT, and the increase of SOC and N_t was +28% and +33%, respectively, in 2016. The alkaline phosphatase levelled out already 6 years after the start of the experiment, whereas, as noted above, SOC increased for 13 years before levelling out. This confirms findings from several researchers (D'Hose et al. 2018; Friedel, Munch, and Fischer 1996; Tscherko and Kandeler 1999; Spiegel et al. 2007) that microbial analyses are more sensitive to detect management changes than element concentrations.

4.2.2 | PLFAs

Our finding of significantly higher total PLFA concentrations in RT and MT compared to CT in the top layer has been reported by other studies under different climate and soil conditions (Drijber et al. 2000; Helgason, Walley, and Germida 2009; Li et al. 2020). The total PLFA showed the highest positive relationship with selected enzyme activities (alkaline phosphatase) and soil organic matter indicators, that is N_t , N mineralisation potential, and active carbon, a labile carbon fraction (Tatzber et al. 2015). The positive relationship between total PLFA and SOC, also reported by several authors (e.g., D'Hose et al. 2016; Willekens et al. 2014), may point to more resources for soil microbes. No significant correlations occurred with only chemical soil parameters (P_{CAL} , K_{CAL} , CEC, pH). This shows that their relationship with the total PLFA as an indicator for microbial biomass is less evident. The increasing PLFA per unit SOC from CT to MT in the top layer

indicates better living conditions for the soil microbes. This may reflect the presence of more macropores in low-tilling systems, which creates more living space for more soil microorganisms (Anderson and Domsch 1989; Sun et al. 2020). In deeper soil layers, the total PLFA:SOC ratio was lower, and the differences between the treatments were minimal. This suggests that the available carbon in the top layer comes from harvest residues not ploughed into deeper soil layers. Less available carbon with depth in MT and RT is supported by the increase in the Gram-positive:Gram-negative ratio with depth because Gram-positive bacteria indicate complex carbon structures (Fanin et al. 2019). However, the higher Gram-positive:Gram-negative-ratio in MT than CT and RT in the top layer contradicts the higher PLFA:SOC ratio of MT compared to RT and CT. The latter would indicate more easily available organic matter. One explanation for this contradiction is that even if the litter supports a high microbial biomass per unit of organic matter, the lower physical disturbance due to less tilling slows the rate of organic matter decomposition due to aggregate formation, contributing to the longevity of microorganisms (Beare et al. 1994; Helgason, Walley, and Germida 2009). Thus, the microbial biomass is less active per unit of organic matter. This hypothesis is supported by the lower microbial turnover rate in the topsoil in RT versus CT (van Groenigen et al. 2010). This suggests that less available carbon in the topsoil in MT than in CT can boost the capacity to sequester C in the topsoil of MT compared to CT.

The fungal community has been pointed out to be less shaped by soil properties but spreading over several soil depths, and these communities are less correlated to local soil conditions (Sun et al. 2018). Frey, Six, and Elliott (2003) reported reciprocal transport of C and N by decomposer fungi, whereby C was transported from the litter into the underlying soil and N from the soil towards the litter layer. In our study, the abundance of saprotrophic fungi markers decreased quickly with increasing soil depth in MT and RT and were similar for all soil depths in CT. This is comparable to the bacteria. Accordingly, fungi are not more relevant than bacteria in low-tilled soils, as also reported by van Groenigen et al. (2010) and Helgason, Walley, and Germida (2009). The arbuscular mycorrhizal PLFA biomarker showed the same pattern, perhaps because this marker also can exist in bacteria (Olsson and Lekberg 2022) and therefore could be compromised. The NLFA, however, was the same over all depths in CT and RT and was only reduced to about half in MT compared to total PLFA, which dropped to less than 20%. This indicates a relatively higher activity of AMF, especially in RT and MT in deeper soil layers as compared to microbes, which are dependent on SOC (see also van Groenigen et al. 2010).

In general, significant differences after different tillage treatments can be seen much more clearly if stratified sampling is carried out at different soil depths. Comparing our mean values of soil biological properties at the 0–30 cm depth and at the 0–10 cm depth clearly shows that the distribution of crop residues has a strong effect on the spatial distribution of microbial biomass and its activities. The most important effect is that crop residues remain near the soil surface with minimal tillage.

We know from the literature that applied pesticides could also be decomposed more quickly with non-inversion tillage practices, requiring higher application rates (Jacobsen and Hjelmsø 2014;

Alletto et al. 2010). This is an important factor to account for when farmers are deciding whether or not to change tillage practices.

5 | Conclusions

A long-term reduction of tillage frequency and depth (MT) increased SOC in 0–10 cm without a significant reduction in 10–30 cm. Other chemical as well as microbial properties and the microbial community were mainly affected in the top 10 cm. The microbial biomass (total PLFA) and the microbial indicators alkaline phosphatase and the N mineralisation potential were more affected than SOC. While microbiological properties such as alkaline phosphatase already showed increased activities 2 years after the change in tillage treatments, it took 13 years to detect significant changes in chemical soil parameters such as SOC. Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi, which are not dependent on SOC for energy, decreased more slowly with soil depth than saprotrophs, especially under RT and MT.

This confirms that microbial indicators were more sensitive than chemical ones to detect the effects of tillage changes. The increase in the Gram-positive:Gram-negative ratio with depth indicated less available C in the topsoil of MT compared to CT. This increase likely enhances the capacity of the soil to sequester carbon in addition to the higher amount of C in the top layer of MT compared to CT. A greater accumulation of organic matter, in the uppermost soil layer, coupled with increased decomposition of organic matter especially under long-term MT, may explain why chemical soil properties such as plant-available nutrients tend to increase with MT even in deeper layers. The lower soil dry matter content under MT in the top 10 cm revealed a positive effect on the microbial biomass (total PLFA) and on the PLFA and the NLFA biomarkers for AMF. This could become increasingly important under climate change conditions with higher temperatures and more irregular precipitation patterns.

MT and RT lead to an increase in microbiological properties in the surface layer (0–10 cm), primarily. The stronger accumulation of nutrients under MT in 0–30 cm should be considered in the framework of lower P and K fertilisation recommendations.

Author Contributions

Heide Spiegel: writing – original draft, conceptualization, writing – review and editing, investigation, validation, data curation, formal analysis, funding acquisition. **Taru Sandén:** conceptualization, writing – review and editing, validation. **Hans Sandén:** writing – original draft, visualization, writing – review and editing, methodology. **Sophia Götzinger:** writing – review and editing, visualization, software. **Julia Miloczki:** methodology, validation, writing – review and editing. **Ellen Kandeler:** conceptualization, data curation, methodology, investigation, writing – review and editing, supervision.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.